

Comparative Analysis of Green Investments

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Abstract

Green investments are activities that focus on projects committed to conservation of natural resources and production of alternative energy sources. Green projects have provided about 26% of the global electricity generation in 2018. This study aims to analyze the investments made in green energy globally. It also aims to study the growth in global green investment by technology.

Data has been obtained for a period of 10 years since 2008 from Global Renewables Status Report. Percentage method has been used considering 2008 as the base year and comparative analysis is done. The study shows that overall investments in renewable have been increasing every year by developed and developing countries and China. China has invested 250.77% more in 2018 as compared to 2008. Developing and emerging countries have invested 101.97% more in 2018 while developed countries have invested 261.69% more in 2018 in renewable energy. This shows that investment in renewable energy is highest in developed countries followed by China. Solar and wind power are the most preferred sources of renewable energy. Developing countries have invested into small scale hydro power and geo thermal power in 2018 while developed countries have tried to tap ocean power during the year 2018.

Keywords: Renewable energy, green investments, solar power, wind power, technology, geo thermal power, ocean power

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1. Introduction

Green investments are activities that focus on projects committed to conservation of natural resources and production of alternative energy sources. Green projects have provided about 26% of the global electricity generation in 2018. This study aims to analyze the investments made in green energy globally. It also aims to study the growth in global green investment by technology. There are various sources of green energy such as solar energy, wind energy, bio power, hydro power and bio fuels. Ocean power has not been tapped globally. Data has been obtained from Global Renewables Status Report for analysis purpose.

2. Research Objective

1. To analyze the global investment in Green energy
2. To study growth in global Green Investment by technology

3. Research Methodology

This study aims at analyzing the global investment in Green energy. The paper also aims to study the global green investment by technology. Data has been collected for a period of 10 years since 2008 for various energy sectors such as solar power, wind power, bio power, bio fuels and hydro power from Renewables Global Status Report 2019. The data has been analyzed to find out the growth in green investments across the globe. Percentage analysis considering 2008 as the base year and charts are used to show the analysis. Data has been analyzed to find out the sector which is preferred by countries across the world. The data is available for developed countries, developing and emerging countries and for China.

4. Literature Review

Keerthi B.S.[1](2013) has stated that the government is focusing on utilizing on renewable resources and enhancing energy efficiency. MSMEs need to be more energy efficient to increase competitiveness and support the environment. For the purpose SIDBI and SBI extend loans to MSMEs and thus contribute to sustaining the environment. Inderst, G., Kaminker, Ch., Stewart, F.[2](2012) have studied the role of pension funds in financing green initiatives. Institutional investors can invest in various green projects. They have expanded the scope of green investments. Green investments can be made in different asset classes such as equity, bonds, hedge funds, private equity and commodities.

Luc Eyraud, Abdoul Wane, Changchang Zhang and Benedict Clements [3](2011) have mentioned the trends and determinants of green investment. They have identified the green energy resources where investment is made. Higher level of income boosts investment in green technology. Cost of capital, crude oil prices have a negative impact on green investment.

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Regional composition as well as global investment has changed dramatically. Priyanka Goel [4](2016) has studied the green financial products and services offered in India. The author has mentioned the schemes under green banking practices by top public and private sector banks in India. Various green investments are made in the form of green bonds and green insurance. India has a huge potential to create green infrastructure by creating awareness among investors. Babita Jha, Priti Bakhshi[5](2019) have stated type of loans extended to the MSME sector for green investments by private equity. The green finance instruments should be designed so as to attract local and international investors. This will increase the investments in green energy as it has a huge potential for growth. Xuexian Gao and Haidong Zheng[6](2017) have used the Stackelberg game to address the interaction between regulator and firm. The level of green investment for a firm depends upon the market and operational factors. Increasing awareness about the environment among the consumers can drive the firm to invest in green projects. Kai Wang, Hao-Min Zhang et al[7](2018) have studied the firms in China and found that if the chairmen are politically connected the firm can invest more into green projects. Green practices and strategic development can be combined together.

5. Green Investments

Global investments in renewable power and fuels were US \$288.9 billion in 2018. Investment in renewables focused more on solar power amounting to US \$139.7 billion in 2018. China leads the investment in renewable energy followed by the US. Ukraine and Vietnam also invested more than US \$ 2 billion each for the first time.

5.1 Global Investment in Renewable Power and Fuels

The data has been collected for China, Developing and emerging countries and Developed countries for a period of 10 years since 2008. A total of 181 gigawatts (GW) of renewable power were added in 2018 and the number of countries integrating variable renewable energy is also increasing.

Table 1: Global Investment in Renewable Power and Fuels (US \$ Billion)

Year	China	Developing & Emerging countries	Developed countries	Total
2008	26	30.5	120.9	177.4
2009	36.6	24	107.6	168.2
2010	42.4	35.1	161.2	238.7
2011	45.5	40.5	201.7	287.7
2012	56.5	41.3	152.5	250.3
2013	63.3	35.1	133.2	231.6
2014	89.5	42	155.4	286.9
2015	121.4	49.1	148	318.5
2016	105.1	44.5	144.2	293.8
2017	145.9	58.2	122.2	326.3
2018	91.2	61.6	136.1	288.9

Source: Renewables Global Status Report 2019

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Table 1 shows the investment made by China, Developing countries (excluding China) and Developed countries in green projects. There has been a 62.85% rise (177.4 billion in 2008 and 288.9 billion in 2018) in the total investment across the globe over a period of 10 years, from 2008 to 2018. The investment is in different sources of renewable energy such as solar power, wind power, hydro power and bio power. China has invested 91.2 billion, developing countries 61.6 billion and developed countries 136.1 billion in 2018. The percentage increase has been calculated and shown in Table 2.

Chart 1

It is evident from the Chart 1 that developed countries are ahead in investing into green resources, followed by China. Investment in renewables focused on solar power in 2018. China has been considered separately as investment by China in renewable energy is significant. Investment by China and developing countries are also increasing every year.

5.2 Growth in Global Investment in Green Energy

The data has been analyzed further by calculating percentage increase over the last 10 years. 2008 has been taken as the base year and percentage increase for every year is shown in the following table. The data has been divided into developed countries, developing and emerging countries and China.

Table 2: Growth in Global Investment in Renewable Power and Fuels (US \$ Billion)(Base Year 2008)

Year	China	China Growth in %	Developing & Emerging countries	Developing & Emerging countries Growth in %	Developed countries	Developed countries Growth in %	Total	Total Growth in %
2008	26		30.5		120.9		177.4	
2009	36.6	40.77	24	-21.31	107.6	-11.00	187.66	5.78
2010	42.4	63.08	35.1	15.08	161.2	33.33	316.86	78.61
2011	45.5	75.00	40.5	32.79	201.7	66.83	395.49	122.94
2012	56.5	117.31	41.3	35.41	152.5	26.14	403.02	127.18
2013	63.3	143.46	35.1	15.08	133.2	10.17	390.14	119.92
2014	89.5	244.23	42	37.70	155.4	28.54	568.84	220.65

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2015	121.4	366.92	49.1	60.98	148	22.42	746.41	320.75
2016	105.1	304.23	44.5	45.90	144.2	19.27	643.93	262.98
2017	145.9	461.15	58.2	90.82	122.2	1.08	878.27	395.08
2018	91.2	250.77	61.6	101.97	136.1	12.57	641.64	261.69

Source: Renewables Global Status Report 2019

In Table 2, percentage increase over a period of 10 years has been calculated, considering 2008 as the base year. China has invested 250.77% more in 2018 as compared to 2008. Developing and emerging countries have invested 101.97% more in 2018 while developed countries have invested 12.57% more in 2018. The total growth in investment in the world is 261.69% in 2018 as compared to 2008. The table shows that overall investments have been increasing every year for all countries. In 2017 there was maximum investment across the globe (395.08%), contributed by developing countries was 90.82% and China (461.15%).

Chart 2: Growth in Global Investment in Renewable Power and Fuels (US \$ Billion)(Base Year 2008)

Chart 2 shows that percentage growth in investment in renewables in China matches the total percentage growth. The percentage growth in investment by developing and developed countries has not risen in proportion to total investment.

5.3 Investment by Technology

The investment in renewable energy is in various technologies such as solar energy, wind energy, hydro power and bio power. The study tries to identify which technology is more preferred by countries.

Table 3: Global Investment in Renewable Energy by Technology (US \$ Billion) (2018)

Technology	China	Developing & Emerging countries	Developed countries	Total
Solar power	40.2	35	64.5	139.7
Wind power	50.1	22	62	134.1
Bio power	0	2.8	6	8.8
Bio fuels	0	0.5	2.5	3
Geo thermal power	0	1.5	0.7	2.2

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Small scale hydro power	0	0.7	0.2	0.9
Ocean power	0	0	0.2	0.2

Source: Renewables Global Status Report 2019

Table 3 indicates the investment made in technology by China, developed and developing countries. The figures show that solar power is the most preferred technology as renewable source of energy. Countries also prefer to invest in wind power technology. Developed economies are leading in both solar and wind power investment in 2018. China followed the developed economies. Developing and emerging countries invested more in solar power than in wind power during the year.

Chart3: Global Investment in Renewable Energy by Technology(US\$ Billion) (2018)

Developed economies are leading in both solar and wind power investment in 2018, followed by China. Developing and emerging economies have invested significantly more in solar power than in wind power during the year. Ocean power is untapped and geo-thermal power, bio fuels and bio power is also not much in use.

Table 4: Global Investment in Renewable Energy by Technology (% of Total Investment) (2018)

Technology	China (%)	Developing & Emerging countries (%)	Developed countries (%)
Solar power	28.78	25.05	46.17
Wind power	37.36	16.41	46.23
Bio power	0.00	31.82	68.18
Bio fuels	0.00	16.67	83.33
Geo thermal power	0.00	68.18	31.82
Small scale hydro power	0.00	77.78	22.22
Ocean power	0.00	0.00	100.00

Source: Renewables Global Status Report 2019

Of the total investment in 2018 in renewables, developed countries have invested 83.33% in bio fuels and 68.18% in bio power. This shows that developed countries have also started tapping bio fuel as a source of renewable energy.

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**Chart 4: Global Investment in Renewable Energy by Technology
(% of Total Investment) (2018)**

Chart 4 shows that of the developing economies have invested more in small scale hydro power and geo thermal power in 2018. Developed countries have tried to tap ocean power during the year.

6. Findings and Conclusions

The study shows that overall investments in renewable have been increasing every year by developed and developing countries and China. Considering 2008 as the base year, China has invested 250.77% more in 2018 as compared to 2008. Developing and emerging countries have invested 101.97% more in 2018 while developed countries have invested 261.69% more in 2018 in renewable energy. This shows that investment in renewable energy is highest in developed countries followed by China.

The study has analyzed investment in renewable as per technology. Solar and wind power are the most preferred sources of renewable energy. Developing countries have invested into small scale hydro power and geo thermal power in 2018 while developed countries have tried to tap ocean power during the year 2018.

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